

Design and Development of Hand operated Mulching Machine

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ABSTRACT

Mulching paper laying machine was designed and developed to mechanize the conventional mulch paper laying machine. The mulching paper roll is mounted on equipment main frame and soil covering assembly is mounted on frame structure. This machine is developed to reduce the manufacturing cost and also portable for handling, assemble and disassemble of mulching machine. The various parameters such as soil temperature and Soil density is considered for experimental work. In order to improve growing condition of crops, there are various methods that improve productivity, reduces the water requirement for growing the crops. The mulching paper which is also known as agriculture film is one of the best methods to cover the soil and maintain require atmosphere around the crop.

Keywords-Mulching, Mulchpaper, Crop growth, Soil temperature, Soil Moisture, Soil covering

1. Introduction

Mulching (Agriculture Film) is the practice of covering the soil around plants to improve the growing conditions for the crop. Because of its poor wet strength and price, paper has been found less effective and costlier than plastic. Plastic mulch film is widely used on high value crops such as Tomatoes, Melons, Cucumbers, Squash, Peppers and Straw berries increasingly on lower value crops such as Corn and Ginger. For arable soils, the most effective conservation practices for reducing water loss through surface evaporation are those that provide some degree of surface cover for the soil. Mulch is any material placed on a soil surface for the purpose of reducing evaporation, retaining moisture, reducing soil erosion, suppressing weed growth and providing plant nutrients as the material decomposes. Mulches act as barriers to movement of moisture out of the soil. They can be either organic (e.g. straw, wood chips, peat) or man-made (e.g. transparent or opaque plastic). Besides keeping the moisture in the soil, mulches can also enhance soil temperature; reduce the spread of soil borne diseases; reduce weed growth; reduce soil erosion); and provide nutrients and organic matter.[1]

Selection of mulch films: Mulches are the materials commonly spread over the surface of the soil to protect from the erosive effects of the water and fluctuations in the soil temperature and moisture. Mulch films improve the crop quality, water retention, minimization of weed spread, soil temperature control.

Thickness of the film: Mulching film is 7-15 microns thick and has a density of 1250 kg/m³. As such 187.5 kg of mulching film is used per crop hectare. The thickness of the film should be minimum possible commensurate with desired life and strength.

Benefits: The benefits of hand operated mulching machine used for agriculture purpose are listed below:

- Conserves soil moisture, Moderates soil temperature by insulating the soil surface.
- Controls weed growth under mulch film.
- Reduces the soil compaction caused by the equipment and people & Reduces soil erosion from wind or water.
- Reduces incidence of disease by protecting above ground plant parts from the splash that soil borne inoculums.
- Improves seed germination and productivity, and provides conducive environment for growths.

2. Literature review:

The effect of speed of operation on width of soil covers at three different depths of operation. The observations on width of soil cover at different speeds and depths of operation were presented. With increase in speed of operation from 1 km/h to 2 km/h, the width of soil cover decreased from 18.84 cm to 14.96 cm at 10 cm depth of operation. This may be due to the fact that, the machine gets less time to collect and cover soil over the plastic sheet as speed increases. Similarly, for other depths of operation of soil covering device, same trend was observed. With increase in depth of operation of soil covering device from 10 cm to 14 cm, the width of soil cover increased from 18.84 cm to 30.92 cm at 1 km/h speed of operation. This may be due to the fact that more quantity of soil was lifted at greater depth of operation of soil covering device. Similarly, for other speeds of operation same trend was obtained [1].

Effect of forward speed, bed width and spacing of holes: Draft requirement Draft required to pull the developed machine was affected by all the three independent parameters. The mean draft required to pull the proto type was found maximum (among selected treatment combinations) as 86.28kp at bed width of 76.2 cm (B1), spacing of holes of 15 cm (D2) and forward speed of 3 kmh-1(S1). At forward speed of S1, S2 and S3 the mean draft required to pull the developed proto type were 74.73, 64.36 and 54.82kp. The draft decreased with the increase in forward speed. It can be attributed to the fact that when developed machine is at rest, there is a static friction between the soil and the working tool of the machine, friction is higher and as soon as tractor gets into motion, the limiting friction comes into play between the working devices of machine and the soil, at that time higher pull is required to overcome limiting friction while as at higher speed, the limiting friction is converted into dynamic friction which decreases the pull to overcome the resistance against it due to the inertia [2]. They are developed a machine which lays plastic mulch at the exact position on the prepared plantation bed and secure it with the soil. The laying of plastic mulch and hole punching will be done in one pass [3]. He designed advanced mulch paper laying machine, which can lay the mulching paper on the beds of the soil [4] Designed a mulch paper laying machine for tractors to help in reducing the time required for this operation [5].

3. Experimental Work

Components used

Figure 3.1 (a) Mulching paper, (b) Metal Frame (Mildsteel, 1-inch sq. tube), (c) Metal Frame (Mildsteel, 1-inch sq. tube), (d) Trench Shovel, (e) Secondary wheels (2 no's)

(a) Mulching paper

Mulch is a layer of material applied to the surface of an area of soil. It is designed to conserve moisture, improve the fertility and health of the soil and control weed growth. Soil mulching also reduces the need for pesticides, fertilizers and irrigation. The technique of mulching is the easiest practice that you can undertake for your garden that will produce unimaginable results. Mulch comes in two basic forms organic and nonorganic. The most frequent items used in organic mulching are grass, straw and bark. While the most frequently used items in non-organic mulching are stones, small chips of brick and even plastic.

(b) Metal Frame (Mild steel, 1-inch sq. tube):

The metal frame is generally made of mild steel bars for machining, suitable for lightly stressed components including studs, bolts etc. It can be case hardened to improve wear resistance. They are available in bright rounds, squares and flats, and hot rolled rounds. Suitable machining allowances should therefore be added when ordering. Bright drawn mild steel is an improved quality material, free of scale, and has been cold worked (drawn or rolled) to size. It is produced to close dimensional tolerances. Straightness and flatness are better than black steel. It is more suitable for repetition precision machining. Bright drawn steel has more consistent hardness, and increased hardness. Bright steel can also be obtained in precision turned or ground from if desired.

(c)Wheels (4nos x10 Inches):

A Wheel is a circular component that is intended to rotate on an axial bearing. The wheel is one of the main components of the wheel and axles, allow heavy objects to be moved easily facilitating movement or transportation a load, or performing labour in machines. A wheel greatly reduces friction by facilitating motion by rolling together with the use of axles. In order for wheels to rotate, a moment needs to be applied to the wheel about its axis, either by way of gravity, or by the application of another external force or torque. (Size 90/100 R10 Section Width 90 Millimeters Rim Width 10 Inches)

(d) Trench Shovels:

Shovels are versatile tools used in agriculture and gardening for a variety of tasks, including digging, transplanting soil, levelling surfaces, and clearing rubbish. Some types of shovels used in agriculture include Trench shovels are quite popular among construction and road workers. This sturdy tool features a thick metal blade to effortlessly pierce through the toughest rock block beneath the ground. This is why trench shovels are the preferred choice to dig tough dry fields and remove stubborn weeds.

(e) Secondary wheels (2 no's):

Its uses to push mulching paper to the soil. Smaller wheels also have less aerodynamic drag on smooth surfaces, and can be built lighter, making them easier to propel uphill.

3.2 Fabrication & Assembly

Figure.3.2 1(a) Frame Construction(b) Assembly of the machine

(a)Frame Construction: The main frame of the mulching machine is fabricated, often using welding and cutting techniques to ensure strength and stability.

(b) Assembly of the machine: Components are assembled together according to the design specifications. Mulching machine is mounting on the bed size.

Opearions carried out:

1. Cutting operation
2. Grinding operation
3. Welding operation

4. Result and discussion

4.1 CAD 3D Model

The figure shows the conceptual design of machine that was prepared by using design software.

Figure 4.1.1 3 D Model

Mulching machine is used for Farmers and horticulturist use mulching as a method of improving the condition of agricultural soils by covering the soil surface with different kinds of materials. Mulch is layer of material applied to the surface of an area of soil for the purpose of reducing evaporation, suppressing weed growth, reducing soil erosion, retaining moisture as shown in figure 4.1.1.

Figure 4.1.2 Mulching machine 2D drawing (a) Front view, (b) Side view, (c) Top view, (d) Isometric view (All Dimensions are in mm)

4.2 Design calculations

The power of useful work done by an average human on the drive machine is given by the power of useful work done by human being.

Given the data

Bed width =60cm

Bed height=16cm

Width of plastic width film m=1.10m

$HP = 0.35 - 0.092 \log t$

An average human can work on field for 2-4 hours continuous. (Let's consider 2 hr.)

$HP = 0.35 - 0.092 \log 120 = 0.158 \text{ hp}$

Pull force required to operate mulch laying machine

$HP = \text{Pull(kgf)} * \text{Speed(m/s)} / 75$

$HP = 0.159 * 75 / 0.419 \text{ (m/s)} = 28.9 \text{ kg conversion } 28.9 * 9.81 = 283.509 \text{ n/mm}$

Draft required

$D = P \cos \theta$

Where, D = Draft, kg

P = Pull (weight of machine), kg = 64kg

θ = Angle between line of pull and horizontal, degrees =45°

$D = 64 \cos 45 = 33.6 \text{ kg}$

Diameter of wheel = 90/100-10 in inches.

4.2 Total deformation and equivalent stress (ANSYS)

Figure 4.2.1 (a) Total deformation mulching machine frame, (b) the above analysis showing stress developed of equivalent stress 1.169 n/mm² Maximum on the frame.

Ansys mechanical finite element analysis software is used to simulate computer models of structures, electronics, or machine components for analysing strength, toughness, elasticity, temperature distribution, electromagnetism, fluid flow and other attributes. Ansys is used to determine how a product will function with different specifications, without building test products or conducting crash tests

4.3 Performance testing of mulching machine

“Mulching paper laying machine” have been designed for agriculture for laying of mulch film in one pass reducing the human efforts and increase efficiency which results in less expenditure on labour. Also, it reduces the cost required for employee for laying mulch paper on bed.

- Simple working and easy to use.

Good crop yield in low water availability areas.

Figure 4.3.1 (a) Preparation of bed of the soil (b) Arrangement of mulching machine to the bed size (c) Fixing the mulching paper to the roller (d) After mulching the paper to the soil.

(a) Preparing the bed: Is an important step in the planting process. Our first consideration will be to remove vegetation currently growing in your area. Techniques for this activity are sun solarization, chemical treatment, or the old-fashioned method of digging them up. Each has some benefits and disadvantages. Sun solarization traps radiant heat energy from the sun and causes the soil temperatures to rise as high as 140° during hot summer months. This can only be done during summer, and is lethal to many bacteria, fungi, nematodes and weed seeds. Clean the surface of the bed, rake it smooth, and dig a trench to 6m deep all around the bed.

(b)Arrangement of mulching machine to the bed size: Soil should be loose and tilled for proper operation of mulch layers, which are typically not designed for cutting in hard soil. Tillage depth should be sufficient for disks or soil-moving components to work freely without contacting hard soil below till depth, which can easily cause side-shifting. Soil may already be loose in raised bed, assuming mulch is applied shortly after bed shaping. Mulch edges should at least reach the bottom of raised-bed furrows for soil stability. This counters effects from natural settling or erosion of covering soil. At most, mulch edges can be fully buried in the bottom of the furrow for the most soil stability. Avoid cutting deeper in the furrow bottom with mulch layer covering disks, which effectively cuts a deeper furrow.

(c) Fixing the mulching paper to the roller: After arrangement of the mulching machine to the bed size we should fix the mulching paper to the roller, which passes through secondary wheels and mulch the paper to the soil.

(d) After mulching the paper to the soil

- It helps to avoid wastewater and stop the growth of grass.
- Simple in construction and reduces the amount of time taken by the former to lay the paper.
- Increase in Crop Yield, Reduction in Weed growth
- To reduce capital cost, even unskilled workers can use it.

(The increasing demand for agricultural produce and health consciousness among people it has become imperative for us to produce more as well as good quality products to sustain in international market).

From the study it was found that as forward speed increased, draft also increased. This machine was fabricated for laying mulch film on prepared bed for different crops.

6. Conclusion

The hand operated paper laying mulching machine has been designed and developed to reduce the cost and to minimize the man power required. The 3D model and 2D drafting are carried out using CATIA software and analysis of the project is done using ANSYS. The hand operated mulching paper laying mulching machine is fabricated by considering the standard dimensions of 1400 mm width X 990 mm length. The mulching machine is tested in agriculture field and his working as per the requirement of the formers. The hand operated paper laying mulching machine reduces the man power and decrease the time consumption by increasing the efficiency. The mulching machine can be easily operated and adjustment can also be made as per the farmer requirement.

7. References

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